

Original Research Article

Effects of Low Crude Protein (*Moringa oleifera* Pod Meal) Diets Fortified with Amino Acids on Performance and Carcass Characteristics of Broiler Birds

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Abstract

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A four week feeding trial involving 48 four weeks old Anak 2000 broiler finisher birds were conducted to assess the impacts of Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) pod meal on broiler chickens. The birds were randomly assigned in equal numbers in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) to four dietary treatments containing 0, 5, 10, and 15% Moringa pod meal (MPM). Each treatment was replicated three times giving 12 birds per replicate. Feed and water were supplied ad libitum. The parameters measured were feed intake, initial weight, final weight, weight gain, feed conversion efficiency and carcass traits. Final weight, weight gain, feed conversion efficiency significantly ($p < 0.05$) declined with increasing level of MPM. None of the carcass traits measured was significantly affected by addition of MPM. Cost benefit analysis showed that incorporation of MPM resulted in reduced feed cost. However, the net revenue from birds fed diets containing MPM reduced as a result of poor weight gain. Based on the data obtained in this study it is concluded that Moringa oleifera pod meal when incorporated in finisher broiler diets may impede growth rate of the birds. Nonetheless, addition of MPM does not adversely affect mortality and carcass traits.

Keywords: Broiler Finisher Birds, Feed Conversion Efficiency, *Moringa oleifera* Pods, Performance and Carcass Traits

INTRODUCTION

Conventional synthetic feed additives such as antibiotic, growth promoters, anti-oxidants, anti-parasitic agents and anti-fungal agents have been used in poultry feed for decades (Odoemelam *et al.*, 2020). However, they created multiple complications, such as traceability in animal products and resistance to antibiotics in the consumer, which became public health issues (Wallace *et al.*, 2010; Kirkpinar *et al.*, 2011). On these grounds, the use of all kinds of antibiotic growth promoters was banned in animal feed in Europe (Ao *et al.*, 2011 and Nkukwana *et al.*, 2014).

Revolutions in animal feed production gave rise to the idea of phytogenic feed additives (Grashorn, 2010 and Embuscado, 2015). Plants and their metabolites, known as bioactive compounds, play a key role because of their feed additive attributes (Uduji *et al.*, 2020). These bioactive compounds, such as carotenoids, flavonoids and essential oils help to maintain animal health and productivity and also help in to producing safe and healthy chicken eggs (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2020). The primary mode of action of these active ingredients is inhibition of pathogenic microbes and endotoxins in the gut and

Figure 1. *Moringa oleifera* Pods

enhanced pancreatic activity, resulting in better nutrient metabolism and utilization (Windisch *et al.*, 2008; Ahaotu *et al.*, 2019).

Several herbs, spices and plant foliage (such as *Hibiscus esculenta* and *Capsicum oleoresin*) were investigated for their feed additive attributes (Moreki and Gabanakgosi, 2014). Among the plants, *Moringa oleifera* (Lam.) is one of the best choices as it meets all the necessary parameters of a phytogetic feed additive (Rajasekaran *et al.*, 2008).

Moringa oleifera is widely distributed in the tropical and subtropical areas of the world. (Odey *et al.*, 2019). Based on potential nutrient and bioactive compounds, *M. oleifera* is a versatile tree, and is given considerable importance in poultry feed and human consumption (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2018). Its pods are rich in bioactive compounds, especially carotenoids (β -carotene), flavonoids (quercetin), polyphenols, vitamins, and nutrients (Gopalakrishnan *et al.*, 2016).

Moringa pod meal could be a phytogetic feed additive based on its bioactive compounds, which have positive impacts on animal health and performance (Yang *et al.*, 2006; Portugaliza and Fernandez, 2011; Zanu *et al.*, 2012; Ola-Fadunsin and Ademola, 2013). β -carotene and quercetin in Moringa pods ranges from 2.7 to 3.10 mg/100 g and 80 to 150 mg/100 g of dried pods, respectively (Amaglo *et al.*, 2010; Saini *et al.*, 2014a and b). When Moringa pods are added to the feed, these bioactives, along with phytochemicals, enrich eggs have positive effects on the health and well-being of birds. Due of its higher protein concentration (22–25%) and high profile of essential amino acids, Moringa pods can be used as a protein source in animal feed (Ayasan, 2015 and Is-Haaq *et al.*, 2018).

Few studies are available on the use of Moringa pods as a phytogetic feed additive, and on its impact on bioactive z as an additive is however expensive and this however increased the cost of poultry production. In order to prevent this trend, efforts are being directed towards the use of some unconventional and cheaper feed ingredients as additives with locally available, cheaper and quality feed ingredients. The use of *Moringa oleifera* pod meal fortified with amino acid in finisher diets will be a possible way of reducing feed cost and producing

cheaper meat for the populace.

The use of *Moringa oleifera* pod meal fortified with amino acid will go a long way in reducing feed cost and producing meat at cheaper rate. Figure 1

Moringa Plant

Moringa oleifera is a plant that possesses multiple advantages, because different parts of the tree (leaves, fruits, immature pods and flowers) are edibles (Siddhuraju and Becker, 2003). Anhwange *et al.*, (2004) mentioned that rural women in Sudan use *Moringa oleifera* seeds instead of alum to remove turbidity from Nile water. Odey *et al.* (2019) reported that *Moringa oleifera* seeds have antimicrobial effects.

Ahaotu *et al.* (2018) found that use of *Moringa oleifera* seeds reduced bacterial count of turbid mouldy water by 1-4 log units (90-99.9%) within the first 1-2 hours of treatment. In addition, Walter *et al.* (2011) assured that *Moringa oleifera* and *Moringa stenopetala* methanol and n-hexane seed extracts produced inhibition effect on *Salmonella typhii*, *Vibrio cholerae* and *Escherichia coli*, which normally cause water borne diseases. Regarding chemical composition, Compaoré *et al.* (2011) reported that *Moringa oleifera* seeds are good source of fats, proteins and minerals. Moringa is a fast growing, perennial tree which can reach a maximum height of 7-12 m and has a diameter of 20-40 cm at chest height (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2013). The stem is normally straight but occasionally poorly formed. The tree grows with a short straight stem that reaches a height of 1.5 - 2m before it begins branching but can reach up to 3.0 m. The extended branches grow in a dis-organized manner and the canopy formed is usually umbrella shaped (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2013).

The alternate twice or thrice pinnate leaves grow mostly at the branch tips. They are 20 - 70 cm long, grayish-downy when young, has long petiole with 8-10 pairs of pinnae each bearing two pairs of opposite elliptic or obovate leaflets and one at the apex all 1-2 cm long with glands at the bases of the petioles and pinnae (Odey *et al.*, 2019). The flowers which are pleasantly fragrant and 2.5 cm wide are produced profusely in axillary

drooping panicles 10 to 25 cm long. They are white or cream coloured and yellow-dotted at the base. The five reflexed sepals are linear-lanceolate. The five petals are slender spatulate. They surround the five stamens and five staminodes and are reflexed except for the lowest (Ihezuo *et al.*, 2013).

Fruits and Seeds

The fruits have three lobed pods which hang down from the branches and are 20-60 cm in length. When they are dry they open into 3 parts. Each pod contains between 12 and 35 seeds. The seeds are round with a brownish semi-permeable seed hull. The hull itself has three white wings that run from top to bottom at 120° intervals. Each tree can produce between 15,000 and 25,000 seeds per year. The average weight per seed is 0.3 g and the kernel to hull ratio is 75 : 25 (Makkar and Becker, 1997). It is considered as one of the world's most useful trees, as almost every part of the Moringa tree can be used for food, medication and industrial purposes (Khalafalla *et al.*, 2010). People use its leaves, flowers and fresh pods as vegetables while others use it as livestock feed (Anjorin *et al.*, 2010). This tree has the potential to improve nutrition, boost food security and foster rural development all of the parts of the tree can be used in a variety of ways. Moringa is full of nutrients and vitamins and is good in your food as well as in the feed of your animals. Moringa helps to clean dirty water and is a useful source of medicines. It provides lots of leafy material that is useful when using alley cropping systems (Hsu, 2006).

One of the most important industrial applications is the use of Moringa seeds for water-cleaning purpose (Kalogo *et al.*, 2001 and Broinet *et al.*, 2002). Oil obtained from Moringa seeds is used for cooking and was found to contain high levels of unsaturated fatty acids (Lalas and Tsaknis, 2002). Leaves and seeds of Moringa represent an important source of nutrients for rural populations in certain areas of India and West Africa (Lockett *et al.*, 2000). Most reports indicate that Moringa leaves (ML) are rich in protein and present an amino acid composition, which is suitable for human and animal nutrition (Freiberger *et al.*, 1998). High biomass production of Moringa of over 100 tons of dry matter (DM) per hectare can be achieved under intensive farming conditions (Ahaotu, 1997).

Previous studies indicated that both extracted ML and ethanol extracted ML (800 ml of aqueous ethanol per litter) had high content of crude protein. Moringa contains certain amounts of anti-nutritional factors like tannins and saponins (Oliveira *et al.*, 1999).

Recently, a high degree of renewed interest was placed on the nutritional properties of Moringa in most countries where it was not native (Reyes *et al.*, 2006 and Oduro *et al.*, 2008). This could be due to the claims that it

increases animal productivity as it has nutritional, therapeutic and prophylactic properties (Fahey, 2005). Studies from other countries indicate that the leaves have immune's nutritional value such as vitamins, minerals and amino acids (Anwar *et al.*, 2007).

Uses Moringa for Animal diets

Moringa has proven to be a valuable supplement for animals. *Moringa oleifera* fresh leaves has 23% CP in DM, 12.3 MJ ME/kg DM (Du *et al.*, 2007). Supplementing *B. brizantha* hay (BBH) with Moringa significantly increased milk production from 3.1 to 4.9 and 5.1 kg/day when feeding BBH hay alone or with 2 kg or 3 kg per DM of Moringa, respectively.

Milk composition and organoleptic characteristics were not significantly affected by feeding Moringa. The digestibility of DM, crude protein (CP) and neutral detergent fiber (NDF) increased ($P < 0.05$) in the diets supplemented with Moringa compared to BBH alone (Nadir, 2006).

Sarwatt *et al.* (2002) studied the effect of substituting *Moringa oleifera* Leaf meal (MOLM) for cotton seed cake (CSC) on milk yield and composition of cross bred cows fed Napier grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*) as basal diet. They recorded that when CSC was substituted with MOLM milk yield was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased. There were no effects of substituting CSC with MOLM on total solids, fat, milk protein and ash contents of the milk. MOLM had higher DM (820 g/kg) than CSC (697 g/kg DM). DM degradability of MOLM was higher than CSC.

Adeniji *et al.* (2012) studied effects of replacing groundnut cake with Moringa Oleifera Leaf Meal (MOLM) in the Diets of grower rabbits at 0, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100%. Results showed significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the treatments. Weight gain values increased from the control diet up to the rabbits on 60% Groundnut cake replaced with *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal and there after began to decrease. There was also significant effect of treatment ($P < 0.05$) on the cost of feed per kg.

The cost of feed decreased as more Moringa oleifera replaced groundnut cake in the diets. Profit, gross profitability and feed cost efficiency increased as more *Moringa oleifera* replaced Groundnut cake in the diets. There was high nitrogen digestibility among the treatment although was not significantly different. Some plant leave as well as Moringa leave have been used as feed stuffs for poultry and rabbit as a supplement or partial substitute for the conventional cereal grains and forages. Olugbemi *et al.*, (2010) studied the effect of adding the Moringa and cassava leaves meal on broiler performance and assessment of growth and blood chemistry when feeding levels of (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%). The authors concluded that the inclusion rate of additional 5% can be used in the finisher diet without any adverse impact on the growth, blood chemistry or carcass characteristics.

Figure 2. *Moringa oleifera*

Melesse *et al.* (2009) investigated the effects of *Moringa stenopetala* leaf meal (MSLM) on nutrient intake and weight gain of chicks. The experimental diets contained MSML at a rate of 2% (T2), 4% (T3), and 6% (T4) of the diets (as fed basis) to replace 3%, 5.9% and 8.8% of the crude protein (CP) of the control diet. The results showed that the daily feed, dry matter and CP intake of the chicks fed MSLM diets were higher ($p < 0.05$) than those fed the control diet. Average weight gain (AWG) of birds fed MSLM diets were higher ($p < 0.05$) than those fed the control diet. Chicks fed 6% showed higher ($p < 0.05$) AWG than those on 2% and 3%. Feed efficiency ratio and protein efficiency ratio were higher for chicks fed MSLM. MSLM elicited no deleterious effects in the birds. The results indicated that MSLM is a potential plant protein supplement and could be included to 6% in the diet of grower chicks to substitute expensive conventional protein sources.

Gadzirayi *et al.*, (2012) tested to the effects of supplementing soya beans with *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal, as a protein source in poultry production. The experimental diets contained (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100% *Moringa oleifera* Leaf). Results recorded no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) amount of experimental group white significant differences in feed conversion ratios were noted. It was therefore concluded that inclusion of *Moringa oleifera* meal as protein supplement in broiler diets at 25% inclusion level produces broilers of similar weight and growth rate compared to those fed under conventional commercial feeds. Banjo (2012) determined the impact of adding the *Moringa* leaves meal in broiler diets added various levels of *Moringa* at (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%) . the results showed that there is a difference significant ($P > 0.05$) in weight gain for diet 2% and there were no significant differences in both feed intake and food conversion rate.

Nouala *et al.* (2006) assessed the impact of feeding *Moringa oleifera* on growth performance, carcass characteristics and digestibility of food in broilers and concluded that the following inclusion rates (0, 2, 4, 6) favoured the tested animals performance. The trial results indicated that there were significant differences

($P > 0.05$) between the tested groups in the final body weight, weight gain, feed conversion rate of *Moringa oleifera* as well as carcass weight, chest and abdominal fat. No significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed in carcass characteristics, feed efficiency. Figure 2

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Moringa oleifera pods (Figure 1) were collected and stored in polythene bags after shade drying and grinding for further analysis and addition to feed (Banjo, 2012). The pod meal was analysed for chemical composition according to standard procedures (Mehta *et al.*, 2003; AOAC, 2005). Selenium and bioactive compounds (β -carotene and quercetin) were analysed with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), respectively (Farida *et al.*, 2008 and Saini *et al.*, 2014a).

Experimental Birds

Forty eight (5 weeks old) Hubbard broiler birds were assigned to four treatments and three replicates with four birds each in a completely randomized design. Four levels (0, 5, 10 and 15g MPM/kg finished diet) of MPM was added to the four diets: Diets A (MPM 0%), B (MPM 5%), C (MPM 10%), and D (MPM 15%), with 160 g/kg crude protein and 2725 kcal/kg metabolisable energy.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed through one-way ANOVA (Gordon and Gordon, 2004) using PROC GLM in SAS software (SAS Inc. 9.4). Significant means will be separated through Duncan's multiple range tests (Gordon and Gordon, 2004).

A daily feed allowance of 100g per bird was offered. Feed offered, feed refused, feed intake and mortality were recorded daily and tabulated cumulatively for

Table 1. Chemical Composition of *Moringa oleifera* Pod Meal

Chemical Composition	Proportion	Unit
Moisture	8.05	g/100 g
Crude Protein	18.98	g/100 g
Ether Extract	2.34	g/100 g
Ash	7.88	g/100 g
Crude Fibre	48.00	g/100 g
Minerals		
Sodium	805	mg/100 g
Potassium	2815	mg/100 g
Calcium	291	mg/100 g
Magnesium	251	mg/100 g
Phosphorus	9456	mg/100 g
Iron	53	mg/100 g
Sulphur	137	mg/100 g
Copper	3.1	mg/100 g
Oxalic acid	10	mg/100 g
Selenium	25.71	mg/100 g
Bioactive Compounds		
Quercetin	114	mg/100 g
Vitamins		
Vitamin A-B carotene (mg)	0.11	mg/100 g
Vitamin B-choline (mg)	423	mg/100 g
Vitamin B1-thiamin (mg)	0.05	mg/100 g
Vitamin B2-riboflavin (mg)	0.07	mg/100 g
Vitamin C-ascorbic acid (mg)	120	mg/100 g
B-carotene	2.76	mg/100 g
Vitamin E-tocopherol acetate (mg)	-	
Arginine (mg)	90	mg/100 g
Histidine (mg)	27.5	mg/100 g
Lysine (mg)	37.5	mg/100 g
Tryptophan (mg)	20	mg/100 g

FCR (Feed intake / weight gain) every week.

Carcass Evaluation and Chemical Analysis of Meat Yield

At the end of the experiment, two birds were randomly selected from each replicate. They were weighed and killed. The birds were killed by severing the carotic arteries. The birds were bled and immersed in hot water for 5 minutes to loosen feathers. The de-feathered carcass was weighed. After dressing, the following weights were taken: carcass weight, dressed weight, gizzard, liver, heart, neck, shanks, and intestine. The crude protein, crude fat and ash composition of thigh meat was also determined using the methods of AOAC (1990). Table 1,2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Performance and Carcass Characteristics

The final body weight (FBW), mean body weight gain,

feed conversion efficiency declined significantly ($P < 0.05$) with the dietary inclusion of MPM. Olugbemi *et al.* (2010) also reported a decline in final weight and weight gain with increasing level in diet when they included Moringa pod meal in cassava based diets. Nevertheless, Du *et al.* (2007) observed no significant depression in growth performance of 3 weeks old broilers (Arbor Acres) that were fed on diets substituted with 0.5, 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0% levels of *M. oleifera* pod meal. Also, Atuahene *et al.* (2008) reported no significant effect of diets containing Moringa pod meal at 0%, 2.5%, 5% and 7.5% levels on feed intake of broiler chickens. But the effect of inclusion of Moringa pod meal on feed conversion efficiency (FCE) recorded in their study was different from what was observed in this work.

In their study, FCE was highest for birds fed diets containing 750g/100kg Moringa pod meal and declined as the proportion of it in the diet decreased. Ash *et al.* (1992) have observed that inclusion of pod meals in broiler diets above 5-10% resulted in depressed performance as was observed in this study. The health condition of experimental birds observed during the experimental period did not seem to have been affected by inclusion of MPM in diets. Du *et al.* (2007) reported

Table 2. Percentage Composition of Broiler Finisher Diets

Ingredients	Level of dietary MPM (%)				
	MPM ₀	MPM ₅	MPM ₁₀	MPM ₁₅	
Maize	60.00	60.00	60.00	60.00	60.00
Fish Meal	11.95	11.95	11.95	11.95	11.95
Moringa pod meal	0.00	5.00	10.00	10.00	15.00
Soybean meal	13.00	13.00	13.00	13.00	13.00
Wheat bran	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00
Oyster shell	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Fortified Amino Acid	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Vit/mineral premix	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Salt	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Di-calcium phosphate	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Proximate analysis %DM					
Crude protein	18.73	18.59	18.06	18.88	18.88
Crude fibre	3.11	4.00	4.68	5.58	5.58
Ether extract	3.89	3.78	3.73	3.80	3.80
Ash	13.24	14.38	14.54	14.97	14.97
NFE	59.03	59.25	58.99	56.77	56.77
Calculated composition (%)					
Calcium	1.02	1.08	1.18	1.30	1.30
Available phosphorus	0.64	0.59	0.55	0.55	0.55
Lysine	1.22	1.04	0.87	0.77	0.77
Methionine	0.36	0.32	0.29	0.29	0.29
ME (kcal/kg)	2749.00	2767.00	2698.00	2709.00	2709.00

*Composition of vitamin/mineral premix per kg: Vitamin E, 25mg; Vitamin A, 6250 IU; Vitamin D3, 1250 IU; Vitamin K3, 25mg; Vitamin B1, 25mg; Vitamin B2, 60mg; Vitamin B6, 40mg; Vitamin B12, 2mg; Elemental calcium, 25mg; Elemental phosphorus, 9mg; Elemental magnesium, 300mg; Iron, 400mg; Selenium 1.0mg, Iodine 20mg, Copper 60mg, Magnesium 100mg, cobalt 10mg, Zinc, 150mg; Sodium

that dietary supplementation of *M. oleifera* may increase immune ability of broilers. Yellow colouration of body parts such as shanks and beak was observed. This could be attributed to the presence of xanthophyll and carotenoid pigments in MPM.

Discussion

Herb extracts have been reported to significantly improve body weight gain, feed conversion ratio as well as layer carcass dressing percentages (Omar *et al.*, 2016). Photogenic feed additives containing essential oils, spices and saponins have been reported to significantly influence nutrient digestibility in layer birds. Plant derived feeds are believed to possess antioxidant properties that improve nutrient absorption by cells, strengthen cellular defense and minimize damages by oxidative stress which consequently leads to improvement in health status of animals (Van der Klis, 2015).

Results of this study showed that *Moringa oleifera* pod meal inclusion in broiler diets had decreased feed intake but improve live weight gains in layer chickens. The least feed intake as well as the highest weight gain was noticed in *Moringa* pod treated group as compared to other treatment groups and the control thus suggesting *Moringa* pods to be of economic value especially in terms of its probable feed conversion efficiency. Lannaon

(2007) reported high improvement in daily weight gain, final weight gain and profit on the performance of Shaver brown layers given *Moringa oleifera* pod meal.

Worthy of noting also is the work of Du *et al.* (2007) who evaluated the effect of dietary supplementation of *Moringa oleifera* on growth performance, blood characteristics and immune response of Arbore acre strain of broilers. He found out that increasing supplementation of *Moringa oleifera* decreases the contents of uric acids, triglycerides and albumin ratio in the serum of broilers. Hence, immune response of broilers increased significantly. Yang *et al.* (2007) further evaluated the effect of *Moringa oleifera* on growth performance, immune function and ileum micro flora in broilers.

However, *Moringa* seed pod has also been reported to be a source of activated carbon used to treat poisons in addition to its rich source of vitamins A, B and C, protein, sulphur containing amino acids, calcium, phosphorus and iron (Mohammed, 2013) which most likely could account for its nutritive value that led to higher weight gain observed in this study. It is also noted that the improvement in body weight gain in *Moringa* treated group could be due to improved feed conversion or reduced amount of feed required producing one unit of meat. Probiotics on the other hand are live nonpathogenic and non-toxic microorganisms, which when administered through the digestive route favours

Table 3. Effect of MPM on Performance of Broiler Chickens (mean ± standard error)

Variable	Level of dietary MPM (%)			
	0%MPM	5% MPM	10% MPM	15% MPM
Mean Initial Body Weight (g)		260±0.00	260±0.00	260±0.00
Mean Final Body Weight (g)		2173± 23.76 ^a	1860± 1.00 ^a	1460± 90.00 ^b
Mean Total Body Weight		1913±37.12 ^a	1600±1.00 ^a	1200±94.52 ^b
Gain (g)		46.33±0.67 ^a	39.33±2.67 ^b	29.27±2.27 ^c
Mean Daily Weight Gain		125.43±0.97	137.53±7.72	124.50±0.76
Mean Feed Intake (g)		2.67±0.07 ^a	3.53±0.12 ^b	3.17±0.07 ^b
FCE (Feed/Gain)		0.00±0.00	2.22±2.22	0.00±0.00
Mortality (%)		1.08	1.05	0.89
Feed cost/kg diet		5.46	5.88	5.04
Feed cost/bird		6.00	6.00	6.00
Price/bird at 8 weeks (wt/kg)		13.04	11.16	11.28
Value/ bird		7.04	5.16	6.24
Net revenue/bird				3.30

a,b,c,d: Treatment means with different superscripts within the same row are significantly different at P<0.05; SEM = Standard error of mean.

Table 4. Effect of MPM Meal on Organ Weights of Broiler Chickens (mean ± standard error)

Variable	Level of dietary MPM (%)			
	0% MPM	5% MPM	10% MPM	15% MPM
Dressed Weight (g)		1444.00±23.67	1455.00±35.00	1433.00±9.00
Dressing Percentage (%)		81.17±1.40	79.70±0.85	80.03±0.90
Carcass weight (g)		1179.33±19.67	1825.67±12.33	1791.67±29.33
Liver		81.33±5.33	85.00±9.00	94.00±5.00
Kidney		1.00±0.00	1.00±0.00	1.00±0.00
Heart		7.67±0.67	10.00±1.00	8.67±0.67
Full crop		11.00±0.00	11.67±2.67	12.33±1.67
Empty crop		9.67±0.67	9.67±0.66	11.67±1.33
Full proventriculus		9.33±0.33	9.33±0.33	9.33±0.67
Empty proventriculus				8.66±0.67
Full gizzard		9.33±0.33	8.67±0.67	8.67±0.33
Empty gizzard		54.00±0.00	57.67±0.33	60.67±7.33
Small intestine: Full		40.00±0.00	39.67±0.33	40.33±3.67
Empty		126.00±6.00	137.00±10.00	137.00±13.67
		69.33±1.67	68.67±1.00	68.67±1.33
				70.00±1.00

a,b,c,d: Treatment means with different superscripts within the same row are significantly different at P<0.05; SEM = Standard error of mean

the host's health (Guillot, 1998).

The addition of probiotics especially Bactofort® and Anthox® to livestock feed were reported to improve the nutritive quality of feed and performance of animals by (Glade and Sist, 1998). This study supports this finding in broiler birds. Today non-antibiotic growth promoters such as organic acids and probiotics are increasingly being produced and used for animal nutrition worldwide (Windisch *et al.*, 2008). The cost may hinder many backyard poultry farmers in especially developing nations and therefore Moringa pods may be an excellent alternative.

One of the major reasons for increased interest in the use of probiotics in livestock in recent years is because they are natural alternatives to antibiotics and for their growth promotion effects in especially poultry (Bajpai *et al.*, 2005). Rajmane and Ranade (1994) found that the

inclusion of vitamin E and C at 150 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg in poultry diet respectively improved growth rate as well as immune response of vaccinated chickens. Furthermore, Bharali *et al.* (2003) reported that inclusion of selenium in poultry diet markedly reduced feed conversion ratio due to the fact that it significantly lowered feed intake but found it to have improved eviscerated carcass weight.

Contrary to this study, Bhattacharya *et al.*, (1982) reported that selenium yeast improved body weight and feed conversion ratio in layers. In this study however, it was found out that layers treated with vitamin E and Selenium had a high feed consumption with a concomitant least body weight gain agreeing closely to the findings of Chandrasiri *et al.* (2004). Vitamin E and selenium may therefore be of little or no value in enhancing body weight gain in layers.

The decrease in the feed intake was due to high density feed on account of essential amino acids, vitamins and minerals present in MPM which meet the body requirement even with smaller intake. During the experimental period best FCR and BWG was recorded in the T₃ with 10% MPM. This might be due to rich availability of essential nutrients like amino acids, vitamins and antioxidant compounds present in *Moringa oleifera* pods which affect the overall health, production and FCR in experimental birds. The increase in relative giblet weights can be attributed to the bioactive compounds (carotenoids, flavonoids) of Moringa pods meal, which interact with the metabolism and enhance the productive performance by improving digestibility. Some other studies also reported that *Moringa oleifera* supplementation affect the giblet relative weight (Yang *et al.*, 2006). Similarly it has been reported in other studies that Moringa supplementation show positive impact on FCR of broiler birds (Kasolo *et al.*, 2011). Table 3,4

CONCLUSION

From this study it can be concluded that *Moringa oleifera* when partially used with fortified amino acids may hamper growth rate of broiler chickens. However, inclusion of MPM at the levels used in this study may not have any adverse effect on health and carcass quality. Again it was observed that inclusion of MPM in diets led to a reduction in feed cost. The net revenue recorded for birds on diets containing MPM however reduced due to depressed weight gain.

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